

The Influence of Adolescent Reproductive Health Promotion Using the Buzz Group Method on the Knowledge and Attitudes of Class VIII Students of Junior High School 3 South Konawe District, Southeast Sulawesi Province, Indonesia, 2023

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Abstract:- Background: Based on the Central Statistics Agency for Southeast Sulawesi, the percentage of women aged 10-54 years who have ever been pregnant by district/city and age at first pregnancy, South Konawe shows 15% of pregnant women aged less than 16 years. There are several problems related to reproductive health irregularities, namely early pregnancy and marriage, unwanted pregnancies and the transmission of sexual diseases. Based on a preliminary survey at the junior high school country 3 South Konawe, many teenagers do not receive sufficient and correct information about sexuality and reproductive health.

Objective: To find out the effect of promoting adolescent reproductive health using the buzz group method on the knowledge and attitudes of class VIII students at Junior high school country 3 South Konawe District, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023.

Method: The method used in this research uses Pre-Experimental Design with a One Group Pretest-Posttest Design approach. The number of samples in the study was 42 respondents. The sampling technique uses Purposive Sampling technique. The analysis method uses the Wilcoxon test which is carried out using the SPSS application.

Results: The results of the study showed that students' knowledge and attitudes before and after reproductive health promotion using the buzz group method increased. This can be seen from the statistical test value of knowledge and attitudes which obtained a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. So H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that there is an influence of adolescent reproductive health promotion using the buzz group method on the knowledge and attitudes of class VIII students at junior high school country 3 South Konawe District.

Conclusion: There is an influence before and after promoting adolescent reproductive health using the Buzz Group method on the knowledge and attitudes of Class

VIII students at junior high school 3 South Konawe District. Therefore, schools need to provide health education by providing counseling on adolescent reproductive health carried out by school health teachers or in collaboration with community health centers and health services. Collaboration between schools and health workers to form reproductive health peer educators at the school level.

Keywords:- *Keywords: Health Promotion, Reproductive Health, Knowledge, Attitude, Buzz Group.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) categorizes adolescents in the age range 10-19 years. The population of the youth group (15-24 years), based on data from the Central Statistics Agency in 2021, is approximately 44 million people or 20% of the tenth population of Indonesia. Besides its relatively complex population. Adolescence is a transitional period from childhood to adulthood. When viewed in terms of biological and sexual maturity, adolescents are showing secondary sexual characteristics until they reach sexual maturity. Meanwhile, when viewed in terms of psychological development, they are developing based on the characteristics of children as adults [1].

Globally, the numbers of teenagers (10-24 years) is 25 percent or 1.8 billion of the world's population and the results of the 2021 population census show that nationally the number of teenagers has reached 64 million or 27.6 percent of the total Indonesian population. The latest data from the 2014 Annual Review - Unicef, shows that one in four women in Indonesia gets married before the age of 18 [2].

In the world, it is estimated that 21 million teenager women aged 15-19 years and 2 million teenage women < 15 years old get pregnant every year and there are 23 million pregnancies outside of marriage and there are 3.9 million teenagers who have abortions [3].

[4] Based on data in Indonesia, the percentage of teenage women and men who have premarital sexual relations is 74%, and the percentage of teenage women who are reported to be pregnant out of wedlock aged 15-19 years is 16% and aged 20-24 is 8% [5].

National Population and Family Planning Agency, 2020 population census data. The number of teenagers (aged 10 - 24 years) is 67 million people or 24% of the total population of Indonesia, so teenagers are an important focus of attention in national development. In the National Priority Program, contributes to improving maternal and child health, family planning and reproductive health, with a strategic focus, one of which is increasing knowledge and access to reproductive health services for adolescents [6].

Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency of Southeast Sulawesi, the percentage of women aged 10-54 years who have ever been pregnant by district/city and age at first pregnancy, South Konawe shows 15% of pregnant women aged less than 16 years [7].

Researchers conducted a preliminary study at junior high school 3 South Konawe, 7 out of 10 students did not know about reproductive health, reproductive health counseling had never been carried out at junior high school 3 South Konawe and in the last 3 years (2019-2021) there were 8 people Their female students dropped out of school due to marrying at an early age and 2 became pregnant out of wedlock.

II. METHOD

This research is a quantitative research, with a pre-experimental research design with a One Group Pretest Posttest Design approach. This design does not have a comparison (control) group. This research was carried out at junior high school country 3 South Konawe district, focusing on teenage girls in class VIII. The sampling technique in this research used a purposive sampling technique with a sample size of 42 respondents.

The data analysis used is univariate and bivariate analysis. Bivariate data analysis in this study used paired numerical comparative hypothesis testing with 2 data collection times (pre-test and post-test) to see the effect of health education about reproductive health on increasing knowledge and attitudes in class VIII students at junior high school country 3 South Konawe District. If the data distribution is normal $p\text{-value} \geq \alpha$ (0.05), then the statistical test used is the paired sample t-Test.

III. RESULT

A. Knowledge of Class VIII Students at Junior High School Country 3 South Konawe District Before and after Health Promotion Using the Buzz Group Method

Table 1. Distribution of knowledge of class VIII students before and after promoting adolescent reproductive health using the Buzz group method at junior high school 3 South Konawe District

Knowledge	Before		After	
	n	%	n	%
Enough	8	19	40	95
Not enough	34	81	2	5
Total	42	100	42	100

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Table 1 shows that the distribution of respondents' knowledge before the reproductive health promotion intervention out of 42 respondents there were 8 respondents (19%) had sufficient knowledge and 34 respondents (81%) had less knowledge, whereas after health promotion out of 42 respondents there were 40 respondents (95%) had sufficient knowledge and 2 respondents (5%) had insufficient knowledge.

B. Attitudes of Class VIII Students at Junior High School Country 3 South Konawe Before and after Health Promotion Using the Buzz Group Method

Table 2. Distribution of attitude of class VIII students before and after promoting adolescent reproductive health using the Buzz group method at junior high school 3 South Konawe District

Attitude	Before		After	
	n	%	n	%
Enough	7	17	40	95
Not enough	35	83	2	5
Total	42	100	42	100

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Distribution of respondents' attitudes before reproductive health promotion, out of 42 respondents, 7 respondents (17%) had adequate attitudes and 35 respondents (83%) had poor attitudes, while after reproductive health promotion 42 respondents, 40 respondents (95%) had adequate attitudes and 2 respondents (5%) have less attitude.

C. The Effect of Promotion of Adolescent Reproductive Health Using the Buzz Group Method on the Knowledge of Class VIII Junior High School 3 South Konawe

Table 3 The Effect of Promotion of Adolescent Reproductive Health Using the Buzz Group Method on the Knowledge of Class VIII Junior High School 3 South Konawe

Criteria	p-value	α	Description
Pre test knowledge	0.000	0.05	Not normal
Post test knowledge	0.000	0.05	Not normal

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Table 3 shows that the results of the normality test using Kolmogrov-Smirnov with a significance level obtained at pre test $0.000 < 0.05$ and post test $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the data is not normally distributed so that an alternative test that can be used is the Wilcoxon test.

Table 4. Wilcoxon test of the effect of promoting adolescent reproductive health using the Buzz group method on the knowledge of class VIII junior high school 3 South Konawe students

Variabel	p-value	α	Conclusion
Pre test Knowledge	0.000	0.05	Signifikan
Post test Knowledge			

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Table 4 shows that the Wilcoxon test shows that the value of change in knowledge before (pre test) and after (post test) health education on reproductive health was given was obtained by p-value = 0.000 because the data value is P-value $< \alpha$ (0.05), so that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is an influence of promoting adolescent reproductive health using the buzz group method on the knowledge of class VIII Junior High School 3 South Konawe students.

D. The Effect of Promotion of Adolescent Reproductive Health Using the Buzz Group Method on the Attitudes of Class VIII Junior High School 3 South Konawe

Table 5. Normality test of pre-test and post-test data for attitudes of class VIII students at Junior High School 3 South Konawe

Criteria	p-value	α	Description
Pre test attitude	0.045	0.05	Normal
Post test attitude	0.001	0.05	Not normal

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Table 5 shows that the results of the normality test using the Kolmogrov-Smirnov test with a significant level obtained by pre test $0.045 > 0.05$ and post test $0.001 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the data is not normally distributed so that an alternative test that can be used is the Wilcoxon test.

Table 4. Wilcoxon test of the effect of promoting adolescent reproductive health using the Buzz group method on the attitude of class VIII junior high school 3 South Konawe students

Variabel	p-value	α	Conclusion
Pre test attitude	0.000	0.05	Signifikan
Post test attitude			

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Table 6 shows that the Wilcoxon test shows that the attitude change value before (pre test) and after (post test) health education on reproductive health was given, obtained a p-value = 0.000 because the data value is P-value $< \alpha$ (0.05), so that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Thus, this shows that there is an influence of promoting adolescent reproductive health using the buzz group method on the attitudes of class VIII junior high school 3 South Konawe students.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. The influence of promoting adolescent reproductive health using the buzz group method on the knowledge of class VIII students at junior high school 3 South Konawe District

In this study, it was found that many respondents had insufficient knowledge about reproductive health during the pre-test, but the cause of this lack of knowledge was not known. Before the intervention or health education was carried out, there were still 34 respondents (81%) who did not know about reproductive health either from teachers or health workers, so that when providing education there were still many researchers who did not really understand and know about reproductive health. This was known through Pre-test given before health promotion.

After health promotion was carried out using the buzz group method and using leaflet media, there were significant changes in terms of respondents' knowledge. Namely, knowledge about reproductive health before being given sufficient health promotion was 8 respondents (19%), 34 respondents (81%) were lacking and after being given adequate health promotion was 40 respondents (95%) and 2 respondents (5%) were lacking.

When reproductive health promotion was given using the buzz group method, things were presented in accordance with those on the observation sheet, so that respondents could immediately understand and answer the post-test questions correctly. Based on the research that has been carried out, the results obtained for the value of changes in knowledge before and after being given youth reproductive health promotion using the buzz group method obtained P-value = 0.000 because the data value is P-value $< \alpha$ (0.05), so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Thus, this shows that there is an influence of promoting adolescent reproductive health using the buzz group method on the knowledge of class VIII students at junior high school 3 South Konawe.

Based on the results of the research above, it shows that promoting adolescent reproductive health using the buzz group method has an effect on knowledge where there has been a change in knowledge as expected from not knowing to knowing about the need to maintain the cleanliness of reproductive organs and the reproductive process.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by (Sutriana Anastasia, 2020) with the title "The Effect of Reproductive Health Promotion on Students' Knowledge Levels in West Kalimantan High Schools" showing that the overall statistical test results have a value of $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$) [8].

Providing health promotion providing information at a further level can raise awareness among adolescents regarding reproductive health. Health promotion is essentially an activity or effort to convey health messages to communities, groups or individuals with the hope that with these messages, groups or individuals can gain better knowledge about health. In a health education process that

leads to achieving promotional goals, namely behavior change, is influenced by many factors. Factors that influence an educational process, besides the input factors themselves, are also method factors, material or message factors, educators or officers who carry it out, and media tools used when health promotion is carried out [8]

B. The Effect of Promotion of Adolescent Reproductive Health Using the Buzz Group Method on the Attitudes of Class VIII Junior High School 3 South Konawe District

Based on the results of research on students' attitudes towards reproductive health before health promotion was carried out using the buzz group pre test method, the value of attitude change before (pre test) and after (post test) was given health education on reproductive health was obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ because the value The data has a $P\text{-value} < \alpha (0.05)$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

This shows that there is an influence of promoting adolescent reproductive health using the buzz group method on the attitudes of class VIII students at junior high school 3 South Konawe District. Where health promotion is a dynamic behavior change process with the aim of changing or influencing human behavior which includes components of knowledge, attitudes or practices related to the goal of healthy living both individually, in groups and in society. The results of this research are in line with research conducted with the title "The Effect of Health Promotion Using the Buzz Group Method on the Knowledge and Attitudes of Early Adolescents Regarding Reproductive Health" showing that the research results showed that the average attitude before the intervention was 33.09 and after intervention it was 43.56. Further analysis using the Wilcoxon test obtained $P\text{ value } (0.000) < (0.05)$, so H_0 was rejected, meaning there was an influence of health promotion using the Buzz Group method regarding reproductive health on the attitudes of early adolescents at Bani Tamin Middle School, Tangerang Regency.

Researchers argue that thinking abilities related to beliefs and opinions about an object form a person's attitude. Health education using the buzz group method can provide messages that can be received more evenly by students, is very good at explaining a process, and overcomes space and time limitations. The process carried out when expressing opinions and the ability to think about a topic being discussed can influence attitudes and behavior on adolescent reproductive health.

From the limitations above it can be concluded that the manifestation of attitude cannot be seen directly, but can only be interpreted first from closed behavior because attitude is not yet an action or activity, but is a predisposition to the action of a behavior, one example is one of the factors The cause of students' ignorance about reproductive health is due to students' understanding, where students' knowledge and attitudes are still limited and even wrong, this shows that there is a closed attitude. Therefore, in order to obtain an open attitude, action needs to be taken to influence that attitude.

This action is by carrying out or providing health education because health education is a planned behavioral process for individuals, groups or communities so that they do what is expected by educators to be more independent in achieving the goal of a healthy life [9].

The above shows that the role of health education is very important in influencing human behavior in increasing knowledge and attitudes or practices as a result of the learning process. Because health education is a learning process for individuals, groups or communities from not knowing about the value of health to knowing, and from not being able to deal with their own health to becoming independent. Thus, health promotion is an effort or activity to help individuals, groups or communities improve their abilities in terms of knowledge, attitudes and skills to achieve an optimal healthy life.

Attitude formation is likely to be influenced by a number of factors: personal experience, the influence of other people who are considered important, and the influence of culture, media, educational institutions, or religious institutions. What we experience shapes and influences our perception of social stimuli. Response is one of the basics for forming attitudes [10].

V. CONCLUSION

There is an influence before and after promoting adolescent reproductive health using the Buzz Group method on the knowledge and attitudes of Class VIII students at junior high school 3 South Konawe District. Therefore, schools need to provide health education by providing counseling on adolescent reproductive health conducted by School health teachers or in collaboration with community health centers and health services. Collaboration between schools and health workers to form reproductive health peer educators at the school level.

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